

METHODS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article talks about the use of different methods in teaching a foreign language. The concept of methodology was also discussed.

Key words: Language learning, language phenomena, methodology, pronunciation .

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment (in the family, among the public) or in an organized way (in a lesson). Knowledge of language phenomena is studied theoretically. Knowing a language, especially multilingualism (polyglossia), is gaining great importance in our time when international relations are in full swing. Pupils and students studying in the Republic of Uzbekistan usually study three languages. "Most of our intelligent young people have three languages" 1. In the theory of education, these languages are called by special names: mother tongue, second language and foreign language. Those who choose teaching a foreign language as a profession have the task of becoming fully aware of the theory of teaching this language. The science of teaching is illuminated by the science of methodology, the word "method" is Greek and means "a set of methods for doing something according to the purpose". The term "methodology", which is often used in pedagogical communication, has three meanings. The first one indicates the subject of study (for example, "the first lesson tomorrow is methodology¹"), the second one is the sum of methodological methods of education (for example, "I like our teacher's methodology"), and the third one is the theory of education and special represents science (eg, "the methodology is well covered in this manual"). This chapter discusses the third terminological meaning of the word "methodology". There can be three types of knowledge of a foreign language - active, passive and mixed. Active knowledge refers to perfect mastery of all types of speech activity as in the native language. Passive knowledge is the ability to understand spoken and written text. Mixed knowledge is the acquisition of part of the language material actively and another part passively in speech. In psychology, mastering a foreign language is the formation of skills and competences. The term skill can be defined as follows: A skill is an automated component of a consciously performed activity. An automated activity without conscious involvement is defined

as a skill. The concept of knowledge means mastering lexis, grammar and pronunciation in foreign language speech and knowing the simple rules related to them. In the grammar-translation method, all attention is focused on grammar, and the content and vocabulary of the texts are not taken into account. In the textual translation method, all attention is focused on the content and features of the texts, grammar is studied in an irregular manner, and rules are given from time to time.

All training is built according to these principles. Thus, in the textbook of M. Berlitz, the first pages of the book are filled with drawings with plates depicting individual objects for the school audience. This kind of oral opening, involving the introduction of new material in the following paragraphs, is done by the author so that the student first learns the original pronunciation and imitation.

excused because they needed to hear the pattern to be played. Vocabulary semanticization was carried out with the help of visualization, facial expressions played an important role. In cases where the indicated tools could not help, the teacher switched to semanticization with the help of context. Question-and-answer exercises were widely used as exercises.

First of all, it should be noted that representatives of the natural method proposed a system of continuous semanticization of vocabulary:

- 1) showing the object, its image, demonstrating the movement using facial expressions;
- 2) reveal the meaning of words using synonyms, antonyms or definitions;
- 3) revealing the meaning with the help of context.

The methodological principles of teaching the direct method were as follows:

1. The basis of teaching is oral speech, because any language is inherently sound, and the leading place is occupied by sound and kinesthetic sensations (sensations of the speech apparatus), as proven by psychology.

2. Exclusion of native language and translation. This position is based on the fact that the words of the mother tongue do not match the meaning of the words being studied, different concepts and

It was based on studies that express similar things, because each nation has its own worldview, a system of concepts reflected in the language.

3. Special importance was given to phonetics and pronunciation, because mastering the sound side of speech is an indispensable condition for oral speech. This conclusion was made based on the study of the sound side of the language. As a result, pronunciation methods were developed.

4. Based on the position of Gestalt psychology, which is not the sum of its components and the linguistic position of words in the polysemy, representatives of the direct method recommended studying words only in context.

5. It was proposed to learn grammar based on induction in this method. Based on a well-studied text, students made observations on the text and extracted rules. Espersen O. called it "observational grammar". Later, these rules were introduced into the system.

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